

On-The-Spot Spectators' Motivations, Experiences, and Satisfactions at the 2011 TPGA Ever Rich Championship – North Bay Open

Li-Wei Liu, Cheng-Yu Tsai, and Ming-Tsang Wu

Abstract—The study investigated the 2011 TPGA Ever Rich Championship – North Bay Open spectators' on-the-site spectating motivations, experiences, and satisfactions. The research was conducted on a convenience sample of the on-the-spot spectators at the North Bay Golf and Country Club. A total of 200 questionnaires were distributed, of which 185 valid questionnaires were collected, approaching a 92.5% response rate. The data obtained was analyzed with statistical techniques. First, the data showed significant differences in motivations, experiences, and satisfactions relative to demographic variables among the on-the-spot spectators. Second, spectating motivation, experience, and satisfaction were significantly related to one another.

Keywords—Spectating motivation, spectating experience, spectating satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN the Professional Golfers' Association of the Republic of China, the ROC PGA, was officially established on August 9, 1993. The forerunner of the ROC PGA was the Professional Golfers' Committee of the Republic of China which was founded February 7, 1993, and was affiliated with the ROC PGA; the trend of the times has led the Professional Golfers' Committee of the Republic of China to be officially renamed the ROC PGA. The TPGA tournament held a total of 11 games in 2011. The TPGA game with the longest history is the TPGA Championship, this year in its 44th term.

In recent years, the economy has developed rapidly. In addition, the government has implemented a two-day weekend policy, and income and educational opportunities have been increasing. There has begun to be an emphasis on participating in various kinds of recreational activities during leisure time for physical and psychological relaxation. Such trends result in a massive growth of social expectations and concerns for quality, multi-objective, and alternative recreation and entertainment. Besides, the advance of technology in the mass media, like TVs and broadcasting, has contributed to the growing popularity of sports, which are developed in variable classifications and categorizations with the expanding population participating in

sports activities. A wide variety of sports have developed along with the expanding number of people's participation. Nevertheless, engagement in professional sports, which requires high levels of expertise, is limited to a few people. Many others show their enthusiasm and express their appreciation of sports which are popular because of the characteristics of uncertainty, excitement, and drama through watching.

"Spectators" consist of a group that gathers temporarily for the duration of the event to experience to experience a sporting competition, which life is determined by the length of the game [1]. A spectator exists for the experience of observing the sporting competition; in other words, a sporting competition cannot be carried out without spectators.

Since spectators play such a vital role in sporting events, it would be difficult to continue them if crowds stop coming to watch. Consequently, spectators must perceive the value of in-person participation by satisfying people's expectations in advance, and then attempt to meet and even exceed those expectations to make people willing to participate in on-the-spot spectating repeatedly. Such an experience entails emotions, energy, intellect, and spirit approaching a certain level [2]. Zeithaml and Bitner suggest that phenomenal and personal factors influence customers' satisfaction with the quality of a product or a service [3]; Shih also suggests that personal factors, and not just the quality of a product itself, influence customer satisfaction, sometimes, it still involves "personal" factors [4]. According to Tsai, spectating motivations refer to a sport spectator's drive to satisfy certain needs by watching a sporting competition on the spot [5].

Therefore, this study aims to understand the attraction that the 2011 TPGA Championship held for people in Taiwan, what motivates spectators to experience a golf game on the spot, and the spectators' satisfaction levels.

According to the research objectives that are described above, the followings are the four Research hypotheses of the study:

H1: There are significant differences among different demographic variables in the level of on-the-spot spectating motivation.

H2: There are significant differences among different demographic variables in the level of on-the-spot spectating experience.

H3: There are significant differences among different demographic variables in the level of on-the-spot spectating satisfaction.

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H4: There are relationships among the levels of on-the-spot spectating motivation, experience, and satisfaction.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Subject and Sampling

The study adopted convenient sampling and distributed questionnaires to the on-the-spot spectators participated in the 2011 PGA Championship on October 13th to 16th, 2011 on site. 200 questionnaires were used; excluding those incomplete or obviously biased ones, there were 185 valid questionnaires collected.

B. Questionnaire

There are four sections to the study. First, there is an on-the-spot spectating motivations scale, which contains 25 closed-ended questions and addresses the following seven aspects of experiential involvement: passive consuming behavior, on-the-spot participation, personal preference, convenience, development of interpersonal relationships, and recreation and entertainment. Second, an on-the-spot spectating experiences scale that contains 20 questions and addresses sensational experience, service experience, emotional experience, and conceptual experience. The third section concerns the on-the-spot spectating satisfaction scale, which contains six questions. A 5-point Likert scale was adopted for all three attitude scales. Each respondent selected a rating from strongly disagree (1), disagree (2), neither disagree nor agree (3), agree (4), and strongly agree (5). The fourth section concerns the demographic and socio-economic characteristics including gender, age, educational background, occupation status, level of income, and experience in golf.

C. Data Analysis

Using statistical analysis software SPSS 12.0, five analytical procedures were implemented in the study: item analysis, descriptive analysis, t-test for independent sample, one-way ANOVA analysis, and Pearson's correlation analysis.

D. Reliability and Validity Analysis

The collected valid questionnaires in the study were processed in advance with item analysis as a basis for question selection; the analytical results show that, for the on-the-spot spectating motivations scale, $CR = -10.69 \sim -18.52, p < .01$; $r = .53 \sim .73, p < .01$; for the on-the-spot spectating experiences scale, $CR = -12.21 \sim -19.58, p < .01$; $r = .66 \sim .81, p < .01$; for the on-the-spot spectating satisfactions scale, $CR = -14.87 \sim -20.34, p < .01$; $r = .78 \sim .87, p < .01$. Each question approached significance level ($p < .01$), so the study kept all questions in the questionnaires.

The results of the reliability analysis in the study show the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.88 for the on-the-spot spectating motivation scale; 0.85 for the on-the-spot spectating experience scale, and 0.88 for the on-the-spot spectating satisfaction scale. The above mentioned results indicate that the scales of each of the instruments in the study have a high level of reliability.

III. RESULTS

A. Analysis of the Characteristics of a Valid Sample

For the study, 200 questionnaires were distributed; 185 valid questionnaires were collected approaching 92.5% collection rate. Of the total, there were 138 males and 47 females, or 74.6% and 25.4% respectively.

In the age category, the majority of respondents were in their 40s: 118 people, or 63.8%; there were 61 respondents, or 33% in their 30s; 4 respondents, or 2.2% were in their 20s; and 2 respondents between ages 10 and 19, accounting for 1.1%.

Among occupations, most respondents (59, or 31.9%) were in the business, financial, or trade occupations; the second largest group belonged to the service industry (49, or 26.5%); the third group is the professionals (27 people, or 14.6%); the fourth worked in the manufacture or production industry (23 people, or 12.4%); the fifth largest group worked in military service, government department, and academic domain (21 people, or 11.4%); the sixth largest group was in other occupations (4 people, or 2.2%); the smallest group, of which worked in industrial domain, had 2 people and accounted for 1.1%.

In educational background, most respondents' highest level of education was university or senior college (80 people, or 43.2% of the total sample); the second largest group had completed senior high school or junior college (67 people, or 36.2%); the third largest group completed graduate school or doctoral study (35 people, or 18.9%); and the smallest group had a junior high school education or under (3 people, or 1.6%).

In individual monthly income, respondents who made over 50,001 NT dollars accounted for the majority of the sample (107 people, or 57.8%); the second largest group made 30,001 to 40,000 NT dollars (30 people, or 16.2%); the third were respondents who made 40,001 to 50,000 NT dollars (23 people, or 12.4%); the fourth were respondents who made 20,001 to 30,000 NT dollars (19 people, or 10.3%); the fifth were respondents who made 10,001 to 20,000 NT dollars (4 people, or 2.2%); and the least were 2 respondents who made less than 10,000 NT dollars (1.1% of the total sample). As regards golfing experience, 147 respondents selected yes (or 79.5%), while 38 selected no (or 20.5% of the total sample).

B. Test by T-test Analysis

TABLE I
 GENDER OF PARTICIPANT

Dimensions		Male	Female	T	p
On-the-spot spectating motivations	M	3.93	3.65	-3.98	.013*
	SD	.63	.51		
On-the-spot spectating experiences	M	4.08	3.81	-3.47	.009**
	SD	.47	.57		
On-the-spot spectating satisfactions	M	4.25	3.82	-2.04	.005**
	SD	.32	.36		

Note. N=185, * $p < .05$

T-test analysis revealed significant differences relative to gender in on-the-spot spectating experience and satisfaction.

TABLE II
GLFING EXPERIENCE

Dimensions		YES	NO	T	p
On-the-spot spectating motivations	M	3.89	3.75	1.41	.000***
	SD	.43	.41		
On-the-spot spectating experiences	M	4.05	3.85	2.09	.003**
	SD	.85	.67		
On-the-spot spectating satisfactions	M	4.02	3.87	1.35	.224
	SD	.75	.54		

Note. N=185, * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

T-test analysis for individual sample revealed significant differences relative to gender in on-the-spot spectating motivation and on-the-spot spectating experience.

C. Test by One-way ANOVA Analysis

TABLE III
ONE-WAY ANOVA ANALYSIS OF AGE

Dimensions		SS	df	MS	F	Scheffe
On-the-spot spectating motivations	Between Groups	552.87	3	88.12	3.235*	1>3,4
	Within Groups	5500.55	197	102.25		
	Total	6253.42	200			
On-the-spot spectating experiences	Between Groups	27.40	3	45.63	3.574*	1>2,3,4
	Within Groups	792.23	197	55.87		
	Total	819.63	200			
On-the-spot spectating satisfactions	Between Groups	30.07	3	6.52	0.988	
	Within Groups	203.43	197	7.69		
	Total	233.50	200			

Note. N=185, * $p < .05$, 1= 10~19 years old, 2= 20~29 years old, 3=30~39 years old, 4=40~49 years old, 5=Above 50 years old.

Analysis with one-way ANOVA on relationships between age and aspects of on-the-spot spectating motivation showed spectators in their 10s have greater differences than those in their 20s, 30s and 40s regarding on-the-spot spectating, while spectators in their 10s have greater significant differences than those in their 20s, 30s, and 40s in the aspect of personal preference (see Table III).

TABLE IV
ONE-WAY ANOVA ANALYSIS FOR EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Dimensions		SS	df	MS	F	Scheffe
On-the-spot spectating motivations	Between Groups	556.00	3	90.47	2.306	
	Within Groups	6563.54	197	110.28		
	Total	7485.58	200			
On-the-spot spectating experiences	Between Groups	44.04	3	61.01	4.716**	N/S
	Within Groups	824.39	197	71.20		
	Total	888.43	200			
On-the-spot spectating satisfactions	Between Groups	20.07	3	6.74	4.176**	1,3>4
	Within Groups	266.52	197	7.52		
	Total	299.35	200			

Note. N=185, ** $p < .01$, 1= Graduate School, 2= University or Collage, 3= Senior high school, 4= Junior high school, or under.

Different educational backgrounds were related to significant differences in their spectating experiences. Analysis with the Scheffe method found no significant differences. Analysis with one-way ANOVA showed that different educational backgrounds have significance in on-the-spot

spectating satisfactions. Analysis with the Scheffe method found that spectators who had completed graduate school or senior high school have greater significant differences than those who had completed junior high school or less (see Table IV).

TABLE V
ONE-WAY ANOVA ANALYSIS FOR MONTHLY SALARY

Dimensions		SS	df	MS	F	Scheffe
On-the-spot spectating motivations	Between Groups	446.00	3	87.00	2.936*	1>3,4,5,6
	Within Groups	4755.06	197	103.93		
	Total	4801.06	200			
On-the-spot spectating experiences	Between Groups	34.04	3	36.21	1.961	
	Within Groups	644.39	197	39.52		
	Total	708.13	200			
On-the-spot spectating satisfactions	Between Groups	32.83	3	7.54	1.172	
	Within Groups	286.44	197	8.21		
	Total	309.25	200			

Note. N=185, * $p < .05$, 1=NT\$10,000 and under, 2=NT\$10,001-20,000, 3=NT\$20,001-30,000, 4=NT\$30,001-40,000, 5=NT\$40,001-50,000, 6=Over NT\$50,001

There are significant differences in the relationship between different monthly income and on-the-spot spectating motivation. Analyzed with the Scheffe method, the results showed that spectators who receive less than 10,000 NT dollars per month have greater significant differences than those whose monthly incomes are between 20,001 and 30,000, between 30,001 and 40,000, between 40,001 and 50,000, and over 50,001 NT dollars (see Table V).

TABLE VI
ONE-WAY ANOVA ANALYSIS OF OCCUPATION

Dimensions		SS	df	MS	F	Scheffe
On-the-spot spectating motivations	Between Groups	477.40	3	86.85	1.958	
	Within Groups	4792.23	197	93.95		
	Total	5419.63	200			
On-the-spot spectating experiences	Between Groups	39.16	3	57.30	2.437*	1>2,3,4
	Within Groups	720.52	197	62.54		
	Total	789.69	200			
On-the-spot spectating satisfactions	Between Groups	30.17	3	7.52	1.666	
	Within Groups	225.33	197	9.26		
	Total	273.40	200			

Note. N=185, * $p < .05$, 1=Student, 2= Military service, government department, and academic and education domains, 3= Services sector, 4= Manufacture and production, 5=business, financial operations, 6=professionals, 7=others.

Different occupation groups showed significant differences in the spectators' spectating experience. Analysis with the Scheffe method found that spectators who are in the industrial circle have greater differences than those in other occupations: military service, government department, and academic domain; service industry; manufacture and production industry; business, financial and trade circle, the professionals, and others (see Table VI).

D. Correlation Analysis

TABLE VII
CORRELATION ANALYSIS

	spectating motivations	spectating experiences	spectating satisfactions
On-the-spot spectating motivations	--		
On-the-spot spectating experiences	.560**	--	
On-the-spot spectating satisfactions	.566**	.495**	--

Note. N=185, **p < .01

There are significant relationships among motivations, experiences and satisfactions of on-the-spot spectation in the study (see Table VII).

IV. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

A. Conclusions

According to the results, the analysis of each research hypothesis was described as follows:

1. There are significant differences in the relationships between the demographic characteristics of the on-the-spot spectators at the 2011 TPGA Championship and the factors of on-the-spot spectating motivation.
2. There are significant differences in the relationships between the demographic characteristics of the on-the-spot spectators at the 2011 TPGA Championship and the factors of on-the-spot spectating experience.
3. There are significant differences in the relationships between the demographic characteristics of the on-the-spot spectators at the 2011 TPGA Championship and the factors of on-the-spot spectating satisfaction.

B. Suggestions

To integrate and consolidate the primary spectators and to discover more spectating population groups: the study finds the spectating population group of those who are under their 30 account for 3.3% of the overall spectating population, which could be ascribed to lack of time, spare money, interest, etc., resulting in fewer on-the-spot golf spectators. The study suggests holding events such as celebrity golfer's meetings and golf instruction by celebrity golfers, and other implementations that create opportunities to get close to their favorite golf players and, consequently, more potential spectators.

To increase female spectators: the study results find the percentage of female spectators tends to be much lower than the males, and therefore suggests increasing female spectators' participation in golf events by improving services or facilities for women.

To update information on golf: the number of people in Taiwan involved in golf remains small. Thus, it is suggested that golf event planners to increase exposure to golf-related news as well as golf events to encourage people to participate.

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